

Co-ordination Compounds of Dimethyl Sulphoxide with Diaryltin dihalides

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Ten hitherto unknown hexa co-ordinated complexes of dimethylsulphoxide with diaryltin dihalides of the general formula $R_2SnX_2 \cdot 2DMSO$ ($R = \text{phenyl, benzyl, } o, m, \text{ or } p\text{-tolyl; } X = \text{Cl, Br or I}$) have been synthesised and characterised. The infrared spectral data suggest co-ordination of DMSO molecule to the tin atom through oxygen atom of the ligand

Dimethylsulphoxide has been widely employed as a Lewis base in recent years and a comprehensive account reviewing its potentialities as a donor molecule has been published by Gopala Krishnan and Patel¹. Several workers in the field of organotin chemistry have synthesised its molecular adducts and discussed their stereochemistry²⁻⁴. In a short communication, Langer and Blut⁵ have described the synthesis of several sulphoxide complexes of group IV B organometallic halides. Kitching^{6,7} on the basis of nuclear magnetic resonance spectral data has suggested co-ordination through oxygen atom of the ligand. We have synthesised ten new complexes of the formula $R_2SnX_2 \cdot 2DMSO$ ($R = \text{phenyl, benzyl, } o, m, \text{ or } p\text{-tolyl; } X = \text{Cl, Br, or I}$), and recorded their infrared and ultra violet spectra. The results are reported in this paper.

EXPERIMENTAL

The complexes were prepared by dissolving the Lewis acids in neat dimethyl sulphoxide.

Thus in a typical reaction, 2.0 g. of the Lewis acid was dissolved in 5 ml of dimethyl sulphoxide and warmed on a water bath for 15 mins. The complex crystallised out on cooling and the excess of DMSO was removed under reduced pressure at 50°. The solid product was recrystallised from benzene.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The melting points and the analytical data of the compounds are summarised in the tabular form.

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TABLE

Experimental data of diaryltin dihalide-2(dimethylsulphoxide)

$R_2SnX_2 \cdot 2DMSO$	m.p. °C	C(%) Found (Calcd)	H(%) Found (Calcd)	Sn(%) Found (Calcd)
$R = C_6H_5 \quad X = Br$	145	32.1	3.6	19.9
		(32.6)	(3.7)	(20.2)
I	135	28.6	3.4	16.8
		(28.1)	(3.2)	(17.4)
$C_6H_5CH_2$	Cl	40.0	5.0	21.9
		(40.9)	(4.9)	(22.4)
$o-C_6H_4CH_2$	Cl	41.2	4.6	22.8
		(40.9)	(4.9)	(22.4)
	Br	110	36.0	3.8
		(35.0)	(4.2)	(19.3)
I	68-70	31.0	3.0	16.0
		(30.3)	(3.6)	(16.7)
$m-C_6H_4CH_2$	Cl	41.2	4.9	22.0
		(40.9)	(4.9)	(22.4)
$p-C_6H_4CH_2$	Cl	40.1	4.6	23.0
		(40.9)	(4.9)	(22.4)
	Br	165	35.7	3.8
		(35.0)	(4.2)	(19.3)
I	126	30.1	3.2	15.9
		(30.3)	(3.6)	(16.7)

The chloride complexes are white, while the corresponding bromides and iodides are pale yellow crystalline solids. They are soluble in common organic solvents such as benzene, acetone, ethylacetate etc., thermally stable at room temperature and are unaffected by atmospheric oxygen and moisture. Their molecular weights determined cryscopically in benzene show slight dissociation in solution. The conductance data in nitrobenzene indicate them to be non-electrolytes.

Infrared Spectra : The infrared spectra of the complexes were recorded as KBr disc in the range $4000-400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The $S = O$ stretching frequency of pure dimethyl Sulphoxide at 1045 cm^{-1} shifts to $943 \pm 7 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of the complexes. This lowering may be attributed to the co-ordination of oxygen atom of dimethyl sulphoxide to tin. The

absorptions due to asymmetric and symmetric stretchings of the C-S mode of vibration in the spectrum of the free ligand are identified at 705 and 665 cm^{-1} respectively. Due to weak intensity of these absorptions and their close proximity to the strong C-H out-of-plane deformation mode of the Lewis acid, it has not been possible to identify them with certainty in the spectra of the adducts but a slight positive shift is generally indicated. Two absorptions of strong to medium intensity located in the spectra of all the complexes at 415 ± 3 and 400 ± 5 cm^{-1} are attributed to O $\rightarrow$ Sn vibration indicating a co-ordination from the oxygen atom of the ligand to the tin atom.

The ultraviolet spectra of the Lewis acids and their complexes were recorded in the range 200–400 $\text{m}\mu$. Two strong absorptions around 228 and 266 $\text{m}\mu$ corresponding to B and K-bands of the phenyl group respectively are observed and there is no significant change on complexation.

On the basis of analytical and spectral data it can be concluded that the complexes are hexa-coordinated in which donation of electron pairs from oxygen atom of the ligand molecule to the tin atom has taken place.

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